

LOVING THEM WAS RED: A QUALITATIVE ANALYSIS ON WHY YOUNG ADULT WOMEN CHOSE TO STAY IN A TOXIC RELATIONSHIP

PSYCHOLOGY AND EDUCATION: A MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL

Volume: 25

Issue 3

Pages: 498-507

Document ID: 2024PEMJ2363

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.13773244

Manuscript Accepted: 08-02-2024

Loving Them Was Red: A Qualitative Analysis on Why Young Adult Women Chose to Stay in a Toxic Relationship

Eule Adrienne G. Aquino,* April Joyce C. Dela Cruz, Rowena P. Huerto, Gloria Marie P. Lintuco
Jorgen Mikhaela D. Mendoza, Jessa May C. Obing, Kate Annedre C. Padilla, Hianny Andrea A. Sanchez
Drinnie Angeline P. Tutanés, Hardie Gieben M. Cruz
For affiliations and correspondence, see the last page.

Abstract

Young Filipino women are susceptible to engaging in toxic relationships. The socio-cultural development maintained throughout the years of conservative ideology in the Philippines has retained a hostile dynamic towards women, specifically in the intimate connection they share with their given sex. The researchers aim to explore traditional perspectives and the hierarchy of gender roles that contribute to the abuse of young women in the National Capital Region (NCR) of the Philippines. Correspondingly, using a phenomenological approach, six (6) young Filipino women aged eighteen to twenty-five years (18-25) were gathered using the purposive sampling technique and then interviewed with a validated research tool. The findings showed a prevalence of social influences, expectations, tolerance, and manipulation as leading causes for remaining in a toxic relationship; all women engaged in specific coping mechanisms towards their partner to extend their connection. Identity and autonomy diminished throughout the relationships, with separation and a re-evaluation of self-worth being the process of healing. Significantly, their experience was unfortunate, yet they expressed that abuse is one of the means to maintain the established gender role of young Filipino women. Nevertheless, support groups and other coping strategies should persevere for life after the toxic relationship.

Keywords: *toxic relationship, young women, abuse*

Introduction

In modern relational dynamics, the term "toxic relationship" has garnered much attention, most characterized by feelings of insecurity, misunderstanding, hostility, and a palpable lack of support. At its core, a relationship is deemed toxic when it demonstrably jeopardizes an individual's mental, emotional, and physical well-being (Scott, 2022). Correspondingly, most women stay in a toxic relationship since they see a faint hope that there will be an improvement in their relationship with their partner. This shows that they waited a long time in exchange for staying in a toxic relationship. Moreover, they ignore all the manipulation, abuse, gaslighting, or "red flags" that are not acceptable to people around them (Chee, 2021). The signs of a toxic relationship can be subtle or obvious, depending on the nature of the relationship (Manly, 2022). Those women who experience emotional and physical abuse may have serious or long-term effects on their physical and mental health, and they may feel powerless, anxious, guilty, etc. (WomensLaw Org. 2021).

The Philippines is widely regarded to be a conservative country, based on the traditional family hierarchy built on centuries of Spanish Catholic influence. This hierarchy forces women into roles that only allow them to integrate into the family. Despite the ratio of men and women being 50.6% and 49.4% respectively, according to the Philippine Statistics Authority (2022), as stated in Trade Economics (2023), the worker gender population sits at 65.08% for men and 34.92% for women, an incredibly disparaging statistic for the modern age. The researchers can interpret this with the number of married couples that are in the Philippines, where 33.9 million Filipinos are said to be married (PSA, 2022), that nearly seven out of ten couples have men as the main working force of the family. This statistic makes sense as it assumes that most women stay at home and build their lives for themselves or just for a partner. Those in abusive relationships are advised to keep quiet because they love their partners and children or are unaware of or fear being scandalized by the community (Lagsa, 2022). The researchers find the possible population of undocumented cases of abuse to be disheartening, where the study of their experience would benefit every other woman who shares the same struggles as they do, the organizations that aim to help their cases, and the families bereaved by abuses that resulted in their loss.

There are many reasons why young adult women are in toxic relationships. As reported by the study "Why I Stayed/Left: An Analysis of Voices of Intimate Partner Violence on Social Media" there are eight reasons why women choose to stay in abusive relationships. These reasons are Self-Deception and Distortion, Self-Worth, Fear, Savior, Family Expectations and Experiences, Financial, and Isolation or No Social Support. Research done by Karakurt and Silver shows that older women report less emotional abuse than older men. Emotional abuse is more common among young people, and young women are more likely to be isolated. Even more than that, women in general experienced more instances of property damage compared to men, and this increased as they got older. If a young adult woman experiences an abusive relationship, there can be serious effects, such as harm to health. The study by Sanz-Barbero et al. (2019) shows that young women are at a high risk of violence, specifically in the psychological aspect. They may develop different psychological conditions or disorders, such as anxiety, depression, and traumas. Although the elderly also encounter the harmful effects of abuse, we cannot say that young adults' physical, mental, and emotional abuse experiences are less severe. Furthermore, the study by Klencakova et al. (2021) states that abusive relationships may result in low performance either in school or at work. Young adult women in abusive relationships are most likely to develop disturbed mindsets and low self-esteem, which can lead to them losing their

jobs, dropping out of school, and behaving inappropriately.

Evidently, people in a toxic relationship have different experiences that are filled with the narratives of unfortunate circumstances. An article by Lamothe (2019), characterizes the observable behaviors in a toxic relationship. Lack of support between partners is one of them, and they see their partner's achievements as competition. Unfortunately, they don't show up for their partners at important events, and they don't feel happy, proud, and encouraging for their partners—instead, they only care about themselves. The other is having toxic communications with each other, which paints a picture of a conversation filled with negative comments, arguments, and hostility. As a result, some relationships can develop misunderstandings, become unhealthy, and eventually lead to breakups or severance. Additionally, controlling behaviors can exacerbate relationship toxicity and make a person feel suffocated by their partner. Seeing this in a real-life scenario or Filipino teleseryes, the woman is told by the man how to act, feel, and think—treating them as if robot (Comendador, 2023). Most importantly, a pattern of disrespect can raise red flags for a partner to exhibit this behavior in the relationship. Different grounds could indicate disrespect—it could stem from being constantly late, "forgetting" about events, bringing up pessimistic conversations, etc. Due to these characteristics of toxic relationships, these causes can lead to a variety of reasons that further increase the likelihood that an individual will fall into an unhealthy and unromantic romance.

Meanwhile, many people remain trapped in toxic relationships. Many people persevere even when suffering physical and emotional harm. In a toxic relationship, you may often feel tired or sad after spending time with your partner, which may be a sign that something must change, says relationship therapist Jor-El Caraballo. Although they still love their partner, the relationship may not be happy at all now. You two always seem to get on each other's nerves or can't seem to stop bickering over insignificant things. As cited by (Lamothe, 2023), you might even be worried about the concept of it rather than looking forward to seeing them like you were before. The cycle of abuse, characterized by periods of tension, abuse, and reconciliation, often obscures clarity, giving rise to false hope. Toxic relationships are characterized by patterns of abusive or harmful behavior in which one or both parties may exhibit manipulative, controlling, or demeaning behaviors toward the other. As Kane (2020) mentioned, patterns often require repeated activities, tasks, or actions that are performed regularly and often do not require much thought. A lot of daily conduct is automatic; it is something that is done so frequently that it feels natural and has no inherent negative consequences. Or perhaps there is a behavior that someone doesn't want to change because it comes with a reward. Additionally, detrimental behavioral patterns are frequently automatic, don't always manifest as negative intrinsically, and are more likely to persist due to the related reward. However, certain behaviors may persist not because they're beneficial but due to an associated reward or reinforcement. It's essential to recognize and assess these patterns, as they can perpetuate the cycle of toxicity and hinder personal growth or the potential for healthier interpersonal dynamics.

As claimed by a 2017 study by the Philippines Statistics Authority, 1 in 4 Filipino women between the ages of 15 and 49 reported having abusive or toxic relationships with their husbands or partners, and it was noted that this could occur to anyone at any time. Abuse in a relationship can take the form of verbal, sexual, emotional, or physical violence. Conflict in a relationship can have wide-ranging effects on a person. It has been linked to harmful health effects, as believed by research. In one study, "stable negative social exchanges"—otherwise known as persistent or repeated conflict—were found to be significantly associated with poorer self-rated health, more functional limitations, and a greater number of health conditions. It can cause emotional and psychological distress. More than that, a woman may go through trauma, and if the trauma is not resolved, the wounds will continue to grow, and there will be frequent or unexpected triggers that will cause emotional reactions. It will distort a woman's perception to start normalizing abusive behavior and lead her to believe that she deserves it and that it is completely normal. Women will find it more challenging to seek help and end the relationship due to their sense of helplessness and dependence. Furthermore, the effects of these may result in more harm or injury. They may also find it difficult to continue pursuing their goals or dreams because of negativity, stress, and pain. It can hinder personal growth, reduce self-confidence, and cause a loss of self-awareness. Hence, if mistreatment and violence remain unresolved, the percentage of young adult women who stay in toxic relationships will keep rising, will result in worsening physical and mental health, perpetuate harmful norms and expectations, reduce the chances of breaking the cycle, lower quality of life, and hinder our society from creating and maintaining a healthy environment and relationships.

Research Questions

This study aimed to explore the lived experiences of young adult women's decision to stay in a toxic relationship. Specifically, this study sought to answer the central question:

1. What are the lived experiences of young adult women who chose to stay in a toxic relationship?

Literature Review

Numerous studies have been conducted on the intricacies of relationships, yet the evocative aspect of toxic relationships stands out distinctly. In recent years, awareness of toxic relationships has risen, influenced by digital interactions, societal shifts, and diverse cultural views. This heightened attention has ignited debates, with some suggesting a growing acceptance of such relationships among women. This review of literature seeks to offer a comprehensive understanding of the prevailing discourse and to explore the complex reasons young women might remain in such relationships, highlighting the interconnectedness of emotional, psychological, cultural norms, and societal factors.

Conversely, understanding this global trend requires examining the specific cultural and societal contexts of different regions. However, this view is challenged when we factor in the reason why Filipino women enter relationships in the first place. An article by Abalos (2021), suggests that romantic relationships turn toxic is the deprecation of religious foundations such as marriage. People of the newer generations lessen their consideration of being in a proper relationship as it would mean an increase in spending, where the formation of a family is said to be too expensive to invest in properly. This is further supported by a survey articulated by Cabico (2018), which shows that 60% of women prefer having a stable job, rather than pursuing a romantic interest.

Drawing from these contextual insights, another perspective emerges, highlighting a complex relationship between women and the attraction of toxic relationships. A growing trend indicates an increasing acceptance of such relationships among women. As highlighted by Marauskas (2020), many women are drawn to the thrill and uncertainty in men, even when faced with instances of infidelity. Moreover, certain benefits of being in a relationship may seem to outweigh associated challenges, such as feelings of unappreciation, a lack of intimacy, and concerns over financial security. While these challenges can often be addressed through counseling or effective time management, remedying the inherent toxicity can introduce additional complications to the independent lives of the women involved (Ekoh et al., 2019).

Considering this framework, it is notable that a considerable amount of research has been done about why numerous people stay in toxic relationships. Even so, little research has been done specifically on the age bracket, beliefs, and cultural and societal norms of young adult women who choose to stay in a toxic relationship. Current existing research has provided valuable knowledge of the reasons why a woman would stay in the relationship, not expounding why young adult women choose to stay so.

When examining specific cultural perspectives, it is crucial to recognize the importance of understanding why some Filipino women choose to stay or leave their relationship when they are made aware that it has become toxic. Many factors that may seem distant can be the reason why many women choose to stay in a toxic relationship. In the Philippines, many women were not able to get out of the maltreatment of their partner because of the values they have in their religion or their partners using their religion against them (Bri, 2020). Another reason is that cross-generational relationships with women being younger partners, result in a power imbalance between the relationship, and their older partner often having power over the woman (UNESCO).

Furthermore, despite these early observations, the grounds for why young adult women stay in a toxic relationship has remained unclear. As previously mentioned, the researchers more commonly talk about young adult women or married women who have difficulties leaving their toxic relationships. According to the study by Aziz et al. (2019), this phenomenon is more often caused by the fear of having a broken family or they cannot accept the fact that their child will grow up without a father because of their innate maternal instincts. In the same manner, in the literature review by Herman (2019), the researchers from Griffing et al. (2005) emphasized women tolerate being in unhealthy and abusive relationships because of economic dependence which greatly influences their decision to stay with their partners due to lack of means to support themselves. Another reason for women to willingly endure the pain and suffering of being in a toxic relationship is they want to be a savior of their spouse also called savior syndrome—hoping that they can change them through their love and efforts to save their relationship (Sharma, 2023). Significantly, these are considered the top three most mentioned reasons for women to put up with toxic relationships with their spouses.

These questions remain unanswered; Why do young adult women stay in a toxic relationship in a Filipino context? Through reading recent journals and articles, there is an observable saturation of foreign studies and an unfortunate lack of local sources. In the age bracket of young adults, can they identify they are involved in a toxic relationship? We all know that we have a conservative culture in courting Filipino women—do these kinds of circumstances still apply to their relationship? Or what are the concrete reasons why they do not have an idea that toxicity might come to their relationship? Notably, the researchers will delve into these questions and find substantial answers along with producing a thorough analysis of the narratives of young adult women dealing with toxic relationships.

In addressing these uncertainties, evidence suggests that the reason why victims settle into toxic relationships is because they can become inordinately reliant on their partners due to the numerous control tactics used by the abuser (Barbaro & Raghavan, 2018; Pugh et al., 2018). These tactics are used to exert control over a person by consuming their self-confidence and fostering a deep reliance on the abuser, which makes leaving the relationship daunting. Controlling and gaslighting are among the most frequent tactics; however, the abuser might use a variety of other approaches to manipulate their victims. (Holland, 2022). As a result, a toxic relationship will take a toll on one's mental health if the victim is continually feeling low and emotionally drained. This results in shame, low self-esteem, and emotional pain are likely to happen when surrounded by negativity (Foy, 2023).

Hence, additional studies by Drake and Casabianca (2021) stated that an individual who continues to be in an abusive relationship uses denial as one of their protection mechanisms. Denial prevents the brain and sight from seeing clearly, leading one to believe that abuse is often or typical. Women consider both internal and external influences while deciding whether to go back to their partners. Internal elements include a woman's emotional state as it relates to several aspects, such as forgiveness and childhood sexual assault. These internal variables significantly influence how women make decisions. On the other hand, financial dependence is caused by outside forces. Women who are financially dependent on their partners find it difficult to make decisions because they believe they lack the resources and home to support themselves (Herman, 2019). Chee (2022) mentioned that the state of cognitive dissonance, which fails to recognize or tries to justify the action or information, may be brought on by toxic relationships. When there is a dispute between two people, it could be toxic for the relationship (Wishesa & Suprapti, 2014 as cited by Rifayanti et al., 2022).

Considering the multifaceted reasons outlined, this paper aims to understand and analyze the factors that lead young adult women to stay in toxic relationships. The purpose of this is to learn and gain a deeper understanding of the viewpoints and real-life experiences of young adult women. Also, to comprehend both the reasons why people persist in staying in a toxic relationship as well as the emotional, psychological, spiritual, physical, and mental effects of doing so. On top of that, despite the suffering that young adult women experience because of emotional abuse and other types of violence daily, at least one out of many of them still decides to stay in a toxic relationship for years, or worse, for decades (Why So Many Women Stay in Toxic Relationships & How To Break The Cycle, 2018). Women experience a vicious cycle of abuse and manipulation that keeps them there, and as a result, their physical and mental health may suffer in various ways. Furthermore, this research presents data about the support network and safe spaces where young adult women can seek advice, share their experiences, and receive emotional support from people who have been in similar situations. Through this study, people will learn about their values and gain the skills and confidence they need to end unhealthy relationships. Additionally, the research findings will be used to promote improvements in how society addresses toxic relationships. Programs, community associations, counseling, and therapy services might be involved in this to better safeguard and assist young adult women. In keeping with this, as stated by the article “Overcoming the Aftermath of Leaving a Toxic Relationship, (2023)”, it is critical to take care of yourself, seek professional assistance as needed, and surround yourself with supportive individuals. Overall, this study will raise awareness, teach valuable lessons, and most importantly, assist our society and community in talking about this issue. By promoting action, this study will contribute to a reduction in the number of young adult women who experience toxic relationships.

Methodology

Research Design

A qualitative phenomenological study was employed. The focus of this is to study an individual’s lived experiences in the world (Neubauer et al., 2019).

Participants

This study delved deeply into the lived experiences of young adult women who have navigated toxic relationships. According to the study by Paño Quesada et al. (2020), young adult women experiencing toxic relationships like dating violence at the ages of fifteen to nineteen (15-19) and twenty-five to twenty-nine (25-29). On that account, the respondents of this study were six (6) young adult women between eighteen to twenty-five years of age (18 - 25) who have been exposed to that environment or situation themselves and their own words concerning their emotions, experiences, and perception about what they are exposed to. Since the researchers used a phenomenological approach, a small number of respondents may be used, such as one sample of up to twenty (20) respondents (Subedi, 2021). Correspondingly, the researchers utilized the purposive sampling technique to focus on the specific issue and obtain in-depth information about it. The purposive sampling technique was employed to achieve detailed insights into this specific issue.

Instrument

Interviews were conducted using a semi-structured interview questionnaire developed by the researchers. The researchers considered conducting semi-structured interviews as this would provide them with the opportunity to further explore specific themes and responses from the participants. The set of questions is aligned with what motivates the researchers’ aim to answer, “Why do young adult women stay in toxic relationships?” Furthermore, the researchers gathered information from their participants’ experiences dealing with different kinds of negative and positive behaviors, unhealthy habits, and actions during a toxic relationship with their partner. Given that the age bracket of young adults is between eighteen to twenty-five (18 - 25) years old the interview questionnaires would provide a context to their perception of how it influenced their life in different aspects such as their well-being, physical health, social interaction, and relationships with their loved ones. Furthermore, given that the research subject is susceptible to triggers and emotions, the semi-structured interview questionnaires produced for the study were checked and consulted by the research consultants to refine and review the sensitivity level of the questions. The above interview questionnaire constructed by the researchers was then verified by questioning two or three experts and annotated revisions were made to thoroughly locate each issue related to the study.

Procedure

First, a validation letter of the semi-structured interview questionnaire produced by the researchers and an approval letter where they wanted to conduct the study were prepared by the researchers for this study. Correspondingly, the researchers were able to conduct a semi-structured interview with the participants during the data collection. The participants were informed and allowed to give their permission before the researchers started the interview. To uphold and safeguard the participants' security and privacy, this must be done. On top of that, through this interview, the researchers were able to learn about the real-life experiences of the (6) young adult women who decided to stay in a toxic relationship, the effects of their choice on their lives, as well as the motivations behind their decision. This allowed the researchers to use the participants' experiences and details for the study. In the end, they assured the participants that all information they shared with them would remain private and would only be used for research after the data collection process. Before the interview with the participants came to an end, the researchers expressed their sincere gratitude and appreciation to the participants and made sure they had a chance to thank the cities and locations where their research was done and all the people who played a significant role in this research study.

Ethical Considerations

The researchers acknowledged and resigned to the legal rights of the participants, as stipulated by Article VII (7), Section 30 (Philippine Psychology Act, 2009), where the “Rights to Privileged Communication for Psychologists and Psychometricians” states that without the consent of the client/patient, no information shall be acquired by the attending psychologist or psychometrician, extending to the supervision of the professor of the researchers, where the “Suspension or Revocation of Certificate and Professional Identification Card or Cancellation of a Special/Temporary Permit” further states that professional misconduct or negligence in the performance of duties as a psychologist or psychometrician is subject to the suspension or revocation of the certificate of registry (Philippine Psychology Act, 2009).

Therefore, the researchers recognized the “2017 Code of Ethics of the Professional Regulatory Board of Psychology” as the guiding practice of the ethical considerations made in the conduct of the research study, to gather, collect, interpret, and discuss the acquired data with the utmost attention to the rights, dignity, and integrity of the participants involved. An overview of the General Ethical Standards and Procedures of the 2017 Code of Ethics (Professional Regulation Commission, 2017) regarding Article III (3) on Human Relations, refers to that the researchers must uphold “Informed Consent” of Section J, of an individual, whether it is in the conduct of research, assessment, counseling, etc., including the use of electronic transmission. In coverage of the ethical procedure, Article IV (4) on Confidentiality is of great importance to the researchers, as the instrumentation for the participants may be sensitive information they may wish not to disclose. However, the researchers discerned that access to the acquired information will only be used entirely out of the conduct of the research. This article also mandates the researchers to disclose confidential information to qualified psychological practitioners, or the school in which the researchers are being supervised. (PRC Code of Ethics, 2017). Permission to record the proceeding research study shall be immediately asked of the participants, where they will be made aware of the presence of any manner of documentation to ensure researcher transparency, with the primary usage being audio and written documentation.

The researchers must reach an agreement of informed consent that is understood by the participant, where the conduct of research without consent shall place the researchers under prosecution. Additionally, under Article IX (9) on Education and Training, regarding the “Student Disclosure of Personal Information” of Section D, states that Psychology practitioners shall not require students to disclose the personal information, either orally or in writing, the sexual history, history of abuse and neglect, psychological treatment, and relationships, for any case that is a requirement of the program material, training, or a potential threat to a student. This right is further disclosed under Article X (10) on Research, where the “Rights and Dignity of Participants” of section A, states, among other things, that the Psychology practitioners shall respect the rights of the research participants, and their freedom to discontinue their participation at any time. Furthermore, the researchers are obligated to not engage in research that attempts to harm or torture the participants, and the research shall be reviewed before conduct, to ensure the safety of the participant’s rights (PRC Code of Ethics, 2017).

Results and Discussion

Table 1. *Emerging Themes*

<i>Superordinate Themes</i>	<i>Subordinate Themes</i>
Complex interplay of emotional and psychological factors shaping one’s choice	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Prevalent emotions and thoughts • Complacency with tolerant behavior of significant other • Specific emotional and psychological challenges encountered • Socio-cultural norms influencing one’s choice
Societal expectations and one’s coping mechanism	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Role of support systems after the toxic relationship • Societal expectations • Emotional manipulation • Unhealthy power dynamics • Self-empowerment and support system
Role of self-perception, autonomy, self-worth and identity negotiation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Setting limits for self-reliance • Penance for acceptance • Choices of coping mechanisms • Quest for emotional freedom • Societal perceptions and the effects on the challenges of self-expression • Process of healing

Table 1 shows the emergent themes of the study. There are three (3) superordinate themes that were formed, these are the Complex interplay of emotional and psychological factors shaping one’s choice, Societal expectations and one’s coping mechanism, and the Role of self-perception, autonomy, self-worth, and identity negotiation.

Under each superordinate theme, there are various subordinate themes that have been formed. In the Complex interplay of emotional and psychological factors shaping one’s choice, there are five (5) subordinate themes these are Prevalent emotions and thoughts,

Complacency with tolerant behavior of significant other, Specific emotional and psychological challenges encountered, Socio-cultural norms influencing one's choice, and Role of support systems after the toxic relationship.

Societal expectations and one's coping mechanism are composed of five (5) subordinate themes. These are Societal expectations, Emotional manipulation, Unhealthy power dynamics, Self-empowerment and support system, and Setting limits for self-reliance.

In the Role of self-perception, autonomy, self-worth, and identity negotiation there are also five (5) subordinate themes, and these are Penance for acceptance, Choices of coping mechanisms, Quest for emotional freedom, Societal perceptions and the effects on the challenges of self-expression, and Process of healing.

Participants in the study consistently revealed a complex interplay of emotions and thoughts influencing their decision to stay in toxic relationships. Emotions such as fear, loneliness, and a desire for validation were recurrent themes. Extracts from participant interviews highlight the prevalence of emotions and thoughts, exposing the internal conflicts influencing their choices. For instance, one participant articulated this struggle, expressing, *"I grappled with the fear of solitude and the hope that things would improve."* The subordinate theme, "Complacency with Tolerant Behavior of Significant Other," became evident, illustrating the normalization of toxic behaviors within relationships. The challenge of breaking the cycle is heightened by society's historical tendency to normalize and even romanticize abusive behaviors (Ruiz, 2021). One participant highlighted this normalization, expressing, *"I became accustomed to his conduct, and it eventually felt normal."* These insights enhance our understanding of the emotional complexities influencing the decisions of young women in toxic relationships. The acceptance and complacency with tolerant behavior within relationships indicate a normalization of toxicity, with participants describing how they grew accustomed to behaviors that were once considered intolerable. Specific emotional and psychological challenges, such as struggles with self-esteem and pervasive feelings of helplessness, further underscore the intricate nature of these relationships.

Exploring the specific results detailed in the table reveals the emergence of the theme "Specific Emotional and Psychological Challenges Encountered" emerges through participant narratives, highlighting the unique struggles faced when contemplating leaving a toxic relationship. Notably, feelings of guilt and unworthiness surface as significant emotional challenges. The study also sheds light on the impact of socio-cultural norms, as participants describe how familial and societal expectations influenced their decisions, with one interviewee expressing, *"I felt compelled to adhere to what my family considered a stable relationship."* Individuals often grapple with entrenched expectations from family, faith, and culture, making it challenging to deviate from societal norms. To break free from harmful relationships, seeking validation from supportive individuals and environments is crucial (Gillis, 2022). Beyond the toxic relationship, the theme of the "Role of Support Systems After the Toxic Relationship" becomes prominent, emphasizing the crucial influence of friends and family in the recovery process. Participant accounts underscore the empowering role of supportive networks, with one individual stating, *"The presence of my friends helped me realize I could rebuild my life."* The study offers a comprehensive exploration of the emotional, psychological, and socio-cultural dimensions influencing the decisions of young women in toxic relationships, providing valuable insights for the development of intervention and support strategies.

For victims of toxic relationships, expectations from family, society, and religion can intensify an already-existing sense of shame and loneliness, particularly during their initial attempts to flee. Many are either prevented from leaving by this shame and isolation or if they do try to leave, it makes them return. Women are more vulnerable to this type of relationship-shaming than men are, as one of our participants said, *"If you are a woman in that relationship and you are unable to keep it happy and healthy, my social statement is that you have failed as a woman."* Gillis (2022) stated that women have long been taught by both faith and culture that maintaining a relationship is a major factor in their worth. Women bear a disproportionate amount of the burden of compromise in relationships, and when a relationship ends, people often question why the woman didn't live up to expectations. In addition, Holland (2022) emphasized that an emotional abuser targets their victims specifically through manipulation techniques and unhealthy power dynamics. By undermining their self-esteem and fostering a strong dependency on the abuser that makes ending the relationship challenging, these strategies are used to control an individual. Although gaslighting and attempting to exert control are common strategies, abusers have access to a wide range of other methods. *"No matter how strong women talk about what they go through loudly, the thing is that it will change because everyone else who stays quiet pulled those standards,"* said one of our participants.

Otherwise, the fact that women have a variety of coping strategies, such as a support network and boundaries for independence, indicates that these strategies have assisted them in realizing their value and mustering the guts to end a toxic relationship. Lamoreux (2021) indicates that the network of support you create for yourself and the positive people in your life will help you take care of the rest. Undoubtedly, it can take a lot of work and effort to end a toxic relationship. However, it can also be liberating and invigorating. It can let you back into your own life.

Moreover, as women conquered the obstacles of being in a toxic relationship, the narratives of the participants emphasized how they realized and characterized the role of their self-perception and autonomy—along with how their self-worth and identity negotiations were challenged. The participants were taken aback by how they experienced self-blaming on the outcome of their relationship to be toxic. According to Malkin (2021) and Nimmo (2021), due to the experience of neglect, emotional abuse, and mistreatment from past intimate relationships take a toll on thinking of people after being in a toxic relationship where they blame themselves, as said by our participants *"Naawa ako sa sarili ko na, nanliliit ako sa sarili ko na, kasi bakit ginagawa sakin yun?, bakit ko nararamdaman yun?"* and *"Nag-stay ako non kase hindi ko iniisip yung self-worth ko nung time na yun, nag-stay lang ako sa kaniya para kase love ko rin."*

Love ko siya noong mga time na yun.” In this case, the women interviewed by the researchers led them to feel emotions of self-doubt, belittlement, and insecurity among themselves (Hari, 2023). In addition, societal perceptions of women take affect on their self-expression as stated by one of our participants *“Malaki rin na epekto sa relasyon iyong mga taong nasa paligid natin katulad noong mga kaibigan, pamilya so ayun kaya nag s-stay or kaya nag stay doon sa toxic relationship dahilan na rin na iniisip ko iyong friendship, iyong circle of friends namin na mabubuwig and also iyong sa family niya rin na sobrang close ko na.”* This statement indicates an individual’s decision to stay in a toxic relationship because of societal and family expectations placed on them. As stated by Gillis (2022), family and friends contribute to encouraging a person to stay in a relationship despite opening up about inflicting abuse or how toxic it is. Markedly, women are commonly more susceptible to relationship shaming than men.

Furthermore, women who have been subjected to being a victim of emotional, mental, and physical abuse within the course of their toxic relationship it is more often that women would use different kinds of coping mechanisms to escape the pain and agony that were present in the relationship. One of these is having emotional freedom after experiencing emotional abuse from their partner where they can freely express themselves and manage to be in control of their feelings rather than their feelings control them (Martin, 2019). The participants conveyed their journey in the process of healing as stated, *“[It] gives me a lot of autonomy, gives me a lot of self-confidence and I guess what you would say it’s allowed me to grow up a little and generally just grow as a person.”* Correspondingly, they have stated how they surrounded themselves with healthy relationships, renewed energy, and building up their emotional strength as quoted, *“So parang it was that na sinabi sa kinabuhay ko na “hindi mo yan deserve” na parang pina remind niya sa kinabuhay ko “anak kita, you’re great, napakatalented mo, napakatalino mo, hindi mo kailangan ng tao para mapatunayan sa sarili mo or sa buong mundo na may kakayahan ka” ganon.”* and *“Actually isa lang talaga yun pinagsasabihan ko noon which is yung bestfriend ko. Honestly nakatulong siya kase. Although hindi naman siya nag bibigay ng solicited advice but she’s being there. Yung pakikipag usap ko sa bestfriend ko, nare-regain naman yung mga nawalang self-esteem ko.”* Notably, these narratives have shown their progression that evidently gave them the courage to finally leave the toxic relationship and then continue their life with the valuable realizations that they learned from their experiences from their past toxic relationship.

Conclusions

The complex interactions between emotional and psychological variables influence the decisions made by young adult women to stay in toxic relationships to understand why these decisions are made. The careful examination of cultural norms and coping strategies revealed the significant influence outside forces can have on people negotiating unhealthy relationships. This study also clarified the critical roles that identity negotiation, autonomy, self-worth, and self-perception play, as well as how these factors interact in the delicate dance of relationship decisions. In truth, dealing with the complex dynamics of toxic relationships requires a comprehensive comprehension of the internal, societal, and individual factors involved. In addition to adding to the academic discourse, this research calls for a sympathetic reexamination of the social narratives that surround relationships and encourages us to create spaces that enable young adult women to successfully negotiate the complex terrain of love and self-discovery.

This study influenced the creation of focused interventions to assist those in similar circumstances and offered insightful information about the elements that lead to positive outcomes for people ending toxic relationships. This study investigates the coping strategies used by people who have successfully left unhealthy relationships, with an emphasis on the resilience and psychological health of the participants after the breakup. This research lays the groundwork for future studies into the complexities of human connection and resilience by deepening our understanding of the complex web that keeps people in unhealthy relationships.

References

- Abalos, J. (2021, February 1). Do Filipinos still say ‘I do’? The rise of non-marriage and cohabitation in the Philippines. ari.nus.edu.sg. <https://ari.nus.edu.sg/ariscopes/do-filipinos-still-say-i-do-the-rise-of-non-marriage-and-cohabitation-in-the-philippines/>
- Aziz, Nurul Nadia & Abu Yazid, Zaidatul Nadiah & Hazudin, Siti & Wahid, Normilia & Ishak, Maisarah. (2019). Why Do Women Continue To Persevere in an Abusive Relationship?. 8. 1-5. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/340418574_Why_Do_Women_Continue_To_Persevere_in_an_Abusive_Relationship
- Barbaro-Kukade, L., Raghavan, C. (2018, June). Patterns in Coercive Controlling Behaviors Among Men Mandated for Batterer Treatment: Denial, Minimization, and Consistency of Tactics Across Relationships. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/326623394_Patterns_in_Coercive_Controlling_Behaviors_Among_Men_Mandated_for_Batterer_Treatment_Denial_Minimization_and_Consistency_of_Tactics_Across_Relationships
- Bri. (2020, September 23). Religion & relationships. love is respect. <https://www.loveisrespect.org/resources/religion-relationships/>
- Cabico, G. K. (2018, February 14). Love life or career? More Filipinos choose the latter. Philstar.com. <https://www.philstar.com/headlines/2018/02/14/1787768/love-life-or-career-more-filipinos-choose-latt>
- Chee, C. (2022, August 30). Why People Stay in Toxic Relationships. GoodTherapy. https://www.goodtherapy.org/blog/Why-People-Stay-in-Toxic-Relationships?fbclid=IwAR0pqsigQsLGXPV6oCgDnmUkz6wWop3LrMONHv2HfuBycua6kLCBW_nPy0
- Comendador, J. T. (2023, April). When toxic love is consuming you...telltale signs and escape routes. INQUIRER.net.

<https://cebudailynews.inquirer.net/499877/when-toxic-love-is-consuming-you-telltale-signs-and-escape-routes>

Cravens, J. D., Whiting, J. B., & Amar, R. O. (2015, December). Why I Stayed/Left: An Analysis of Voices of Intimate Partner Violence on Social Media. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/283193192_Why_I_StayedLeft_An_Analysis_of_Voices_of_Intimate_Partner_Violence_on_Social_Media

Cruz, A. (2020). What I learned after my five-year toxic relationship. <https://preen.ph/117812/red-flags-five-year-boyfriend>

Cross-generational and transactional sexual relations in Uganda: Income poverty as a risk factor for adolescents. Cross-generational and transactional sexual relations in Uganda: Income poverty as a risk factor for adolescents | Health and Education Resource Centre. (n.d.). <https://healtheducationresources.unesco.org/library/documents/cross-generational-and-transactional-sexual-relations-uganda-income-poverty-risk>

Drake, K., & Casabianca, S.S. (2021, June 24). Loving an Abusive Partner: Why Do I Love My Abuser? Psych Central. <https://psychcentral.com/lib/loving-an-abusive-partner>

Ekoh, P. C., Agha, A. A., & Ejimkaraonye, C. (2019). Unhealthy romantic relationships among young persons. Nigerian Journal of Psychological Research - Nigerian Journal of Psychological Research. <https://njpsyresearch.com/ojs3/index.php/njopr/article/73/71/>

Foy, C. (2023, February 03). Can a Toxic Relationship Cause Mental Health Issues?. FHEHealth. <https://fherehab.com/learning/toxic-relationship-mental-health>

Gillis, K. (2022). Societal Pressure Can Delay Leaving an Abusive Relationship. Certain survivors may face additional pressures to stay. Psychology Today. <https://www.psychologytoday.com/intl/blog/invisible-bruises/202203/societal-pressure-can-delay-leaving-abusive-relationship>

Hari, A. (2023). Tracing out Toxicity: Prioritising Life over Relationships. *Teresian Journal of English Studies*, XV(I), 41–48.

Hernan, A. (2019) Literature Review: Analyzing the Reasons for Returning to Abusive Partners. *The BYU Undergraduate Journal of Psychology*. <https://scholarsarchive.byu.edu/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?article=1251&context=intuition&fbclid=IwAR2jhb1LvpHepQkwnS94Ljdx8hy2nirz7aCa5jrddCEW9wh-XzzMtpDwtX4>

Holland, M. (2022, May 03). 17 Manipulation Tactics Abusers Use. Choosing Therapy. <https://www.choosingtherapy.com/manipulation-tactics/>

Klencakova, L. E., Pentaraki, M., & McManus, C. (2021). The impact of intimate partner violence on young women's educational well-being: A systematic review of literature. *Trauma, Violence, & Abuse*, 24(2), 1172–1187. <https://doi.org/10.1177/15248380211052244>

Kane. (2020). How to Recognize and Change Toxic Behavioral Patterns. *How to Recognize and Change Toxic Behavioral Patterns*. <https://psychcentral.com/blog/how-to-recognize-and-change-toxic-behavioral-patterns>

Karakurt, G., Ayluçarhan, Z., Ergüner-Tekinalp, B., Köse, Ö. (2021, February 05). Regaining Courage to Leave Abusive Relationships: Theoretical Framework. *American Journal of Family Therapy*. <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/abs/10.1080/01926187.2021.1877208?journalCode=uaft20>

Karakurt, G., & Silver, K. E. (n.d.). Emotional abuse in intimate relationships: The role of gender and age. <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC3876290/>

Lagsa, B. (2022, November 29). Many battered women still keep abuses to themselves – DSWD. *RAPPLER*. <https://www.rappler.com/nation/mindanao/dswd-report-battered-women-still-keep-abuses-themselves/>

Lamothe, C. (2019, November 11). Is Your Relationship Toxic? What to Look For. *Healthline; Healthline Media*. <https://www.healthline.com/health/toxic-relationship>

Lamothe. (2023). Toxic Relationships: What It Is, Signs, How to Cope, and More. *Toxic Relationships: What It Is, Signs, How to Cope, and More*. <https://www.healthline.com/health/toxic-relationship>

Lamonthe, C. (2023, July 13). Is Your Relationship Toxic? What to Look For. *Healthline* <https://www.healthline.com/health/toxic-relationship#signs-of-toxicity>

Lamoreux, K. (2021, July 22). 10 Pointers for Ending Toxic Relationships. *Psych Central*. <https://psychcentral.com/blog/steps-to-end-a-toxic-relationship>

Malkin, C. (2021). Why You Blame Yourself for Bad Relationships—and How to Stop. *Psychology Today*. <https://www.psychologytoday.com/intl/blog/romance-redux/201205/why-you-blame-yourself-bad-relationships-and-how-stop>

- Martin, S. (2019, November 16). Freedom and Healing from Toxic Relationships - Sharon Martin, LCSW Counseling San Jose and Campbell, CA. Sharon Martin, LCSW Counseling San Jose and Campbell, CA. <https://sharonmartincounseling.com/freedom-and-healing-from-toxic-relationships/>
- Murauskas, A. (2021, August 22). Toxic relationships are exciting! Medium. <https://medium.com/hello-love/toxic-relationships-are-exciting-e61d8126f5e8>
- Neubauer, B., Witkop, C. T., & Varpio, L. (2019, April 5). How phenomenology can help us learn from the experiences of others. Perspectives on Medical Education. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40037-019-0509-2>
- Nimmo, K. (2021, November 24). When You're Unsuccessful in Love, Quit Blaming Yourself. Medium; On The Couch. <https://medium.com/on-the-couch/when-youre-unsuccessful-in-love-quit-blaming-yourself-d5a2d418530>
- Overcoming the Aftermath of Leaving a Toxic Relationship. (2023, September 1). Psychology Today. Retrieved from <https://www.psychologytoday.com/intl/blog/happiness-is-state-mind/201805/overcoming-the-aftermath-leaving-toxic-relationship>
- Philippine Statistics Authority. (2022, December 8). Age and sex distribution in the Philippine population (2020 census of population and housing). Philippine Statistics Authority | Republic of the Philippines. <https://www.psa.gov.ph/content/age-and-sex-distribution-philippine-population-2020-census-population-and-housing>
- Philippine Statistics Authority. (2022, January 6). Registered Marriages in the Philippines, 2020 | Philippine Statistics Authority. Philippine Statistics Authority | Republic of the Philippines. <https://psa.gov.ph/content/registered-marriages-philippines-2020>
- Rifayanti, R., Sofia, L., Purba, T.D., Amanda, S.P., & Merary, S. (2022, November). Phenomenological Studies: Adolescent Toxic Relationships. European Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/365612892_Phenomenological_Studies_Adolescent_Toxic_Relationships
- Ruiz. (2021). Normalizing Toxic Behaviors Causes More Harm - CAWC. CAWC. <https://www.cawc.org/news/normalizing-toxic-behaviors-causes-more-harm/>
- Santiago Leyson, M. A., Gavina Alpapara, J. B., Charlize Valconcha Cruz, L. L., & Johanna Lim Flores, J. M. (2022). Lost in translation: A qualitative study of the experience of toxic relationships among Filipino young adults and why they choose to stay. Retrieved from https://animorepository.dlsu.edu.ph/etdb_psych/18/
- Sanz-Barbero, B., Barón, N., & Vives-Cases, C. (2019). Prevalence, associated factors and health impact of intimate partner violence against women in Different life stages. PLOS ONE, 14(10). <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0221049>
- Scott, E., Ph.D. (2022) What is a Toxic Relationship? Verywell Mind. <https://www.verywellmind.com/toxic-relationships-4174665>
- Scott, E. (2022). Effects of Conflict and Stress on Relationships How to Cope With Conflicted Relationships. <https://www.verywellmind.com/the-toll-of-conflict-in-relationships-3144952>
- Sharma, C. B. (2023). Why women stay in toxic relationships. The Daily Guardian. <https://thedailyguardian.com/why-women-stay-in-toxic-relationships/#:~:text=Fear%20of%20how%20others%20will,abusive%20relationships%20stay%20in%20them>
- Stubbs, A., & Szoek, C. (2021). The effect of intimate partner violence on the physical health and health-related behaviors of women: A systematic review of the literature. Trauma, Violence, & an Abuse, 23(4), 1157–1172. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1524838020985541>
- Telloian, C. (2022, March 23). Effects of emotional abuse on your brain, relationships, and health. Psych Central. <https://psychcentral.com/health/effects-of-emotional-abuse>
- Trade Economics. (2023). Philippines - Ratio of female to male labor participation rate. TRADING ECONOMICS | 20 million INDICATORS FROM 196 COUNTRIES. <https://tradingeconomics.com/philippines/ratio-of-female-to-male-labor-participation-rate-percent-wb-data.html>
- Why do people stay in toxic relationships? (2021, February 15). <https://www.goodtherapy.org/blog/Why-People-Stay-in-Toxic-Relationships>
- WomensLaw org. (2021). Emotional and Psychological Abuse. Forms of Abuse. <https://www.womenslaw.org/about-abuse/forms-abuse/emotional-and-psychological-abuse#:~:text=Emotional%20and%20psychological%20abuse%20can%20have%20severe%20short%2D%20and%20long,compliance%20powerlessness%20and%20more..>
- Why So Many Women Stay In Toxic Relationships & How To Break The Cycle. (2018, July 28). YourTango. Retrieved from <https://www.yourtango.com/experts/mitzi-bockmann/reasons-why-women-stay-in-toxic-relationships-emotional-abuse-domestic-violence-so-you-can-leave>

Affiliations and Corresponding Information

Eule Adrienne G. Aquino

Jose Rizal University – Philippines

April Joyce C. Dela Cruz

Jose Rizal University – Philippines

Rowena P. Huerto

Jose Rizal University – Philippines

Gloria Marie P. Lintuco

Jose Rizal University – Philippines

Jorgen Mikhaela D. Mendoza

Jose Rizal University – Philippines

Jessa May C. Obing

Jose Rizal University – Philippines

Kate Annedre C. Padilla

Jose Rizal University – Philippines

Hianny Andrea A. Sanchez

Jose Rizal University – Philippines

Drinnie Angeline P. Tutanés

Jose Rizal University – Philippines

Hardie Gieben M. Cruz, MAEd, LPT, RGC

Jose Rizal University – Philippines